

WORKSHOP “CITIZEN SCIENCE TO GUIDE DEVELOPMENTS OF AND BUILD TRUST IN KEY TECHNOLOGIES”: THE SYNTHESIS OF THE TAKEAWAY MESSAGES

Keywords: citizen science, CESAER, open science, natural sciences, technical sciences, researchers, researcher engagement, co-creation, sustainable development goals (SDGs)

By Beate Guba

During the CESAER Annual Meetings 2023 the Citizen Science Subgroup of the Task Force Openness of Science & Technology organised a workshop about the concept of citizen science and its practical implementation at universities. The workshop goals were to:

- Get a better understanding of the interdependencies between open science and citizen science.
- Learn from those universities that have already succeeded in implementing citizen science at an institutional level.
- Share experiences, good practices and knowledge.
- Gain an overview of the European citizen science landscape.

PART 1 – APPROACHES OF UNIVERSITIES IN IMPLEMENTING CITIZEN SCIENCE ON AN INSTITUTIONAL LEVEL

After the opening talk by Jennifer Herek, Vice President of CESAER, Co-Chair of the Task Force Openness of Science & Technology and Dean at the University of Twente, Sabine Wildevuur (University of Twente) in her "[Lessons learned from the Incentive Project](#)" introduced the concept of a citizen science hub, which serves as a fundamental component of the project's framework. She highlighted the establishment of four pilot citizen science hubs and introduced the concept of a fourth-generation university. A fourth-generation university is deeply connected to society, emphasising co-creation, alignment with the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), promotion of transdisciplinarity, and bridging the gap between policy and practice.

Beate Guba (TU Wien) presented insights on "[Citizen science and the UN SDGs](#)", including a definition of citizen science and various levels of engagement. She explained that citizens can provide data for monitoring SDG indicators, which still entails challenges in data collection and aggregation. She also introduced the [OPUSH project](#) that merges citizen science with sustainable urban transformation.

Figure 1: Challenges of Citizen Science and the SDGs. Figure taken from the presentation of Beate Guba.

During the Q&A session, the speakers emphasised the need for a platform that enables an easy connection between citizens and researchers. The prioritisation of citizen science within universities aligns with the evolution of fourth-generation universities, as it facilitates intricate collaboration and promotes interdisciplinary work.

Charlotte Reiff (TU Wien) concluded this first segment by presenting the [results of a survey](#) conducted within the Task Force Openness of Science & Technology. The survey investigated the prerequisites and challenges of establishing citizen science projects at science and technology universities.

GOOD PRACTICES AND CHALLENGES

- „Support from the rectorate is essential for the visibility and acceptance of citizen science projects in the university.“
- „We have several research projects that use Citizen Science but no central coordination or documentation, so it is not a strategy by the university it is strategies by different researchers/research groups due to their projects.“

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GOOD PRACTICES AND CHALLENGES

- „A big challenge at university level is deciding if we are to provide support, create some sort of co-ordinating effort, and take advantage of the push for CS project by the European Commission.“
- „Institution-level resources are not available to support citizen science, including for communication (other than usual outreach around project outcomes).“

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Figure 2: Quotes from the survey participants about good practices and challenges during the implementation of citizen science projects. Figure taken from the presentation of Charlotte Reiff.

PART 2 - PANEL DISCUSSION WITH INVITED EXPERTS PROVIDING INPUT FROM DIFFERENT NATIONAL INITIATIVES AND EXPLORING HOW TO IMPLEMENT CITIZEN SCIENCE IN INSTITUTIONS FOR THE LONG TERM

During the second part of the workshop a panel discussion took place. Invited experts provided insights from various national initiatives and discussed strategies for the long-term implementation of citizen science in institutions.

Panellists:

Isabelle Bonhoure:

Researcher in citizen social science and project coordinator of OpenSystems, University of Barcelona, Spain

Egle Butkevičienė:

Professor of Sociology and head of the Committee for Political Science, Sociology and Public Governance Study Programs at the Faculty of Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities, Kaunas University of Technology, Lithuania

Daniel Dörler:

Senior scientist for citizen science at the Institute of Zoology, University of Natural Resources and Live Sciences, Coordinator of the Citizen Science Network Austria and the platform "[Österreich forscht](#)", Austria

Margaret Gold:

Senior researcher and coordinator of the [Citizen science Lab](#), Leiden University, CS-NL Network, Netherlands

Thomas Kaarsted:

Deputy library director at SDU Library, Director of the SDU Citizen Science Knowledge Center, Denmark, Co-chair of the LIBER Citizen Science Working Group

Moderator: Beate Guba

The following questions were compiled by the Citizen Science Subgroup based on the experience of its members and adapted for the panel by Beate Guba.

What are the requirements to successfully implement citizen science on the project and/or institutional level? How is “successful” being defined?

- Enthusiasm, joy and energy
- Motivation of researchers and citizens
- Co-creation
- Contribution to the quality of science
- Contribution to the societal impact of the university
- Impact on the community
- Number of participants

- Number of publications
- Number of project applications
- Amount of third-party funding
- Multidisciplinarity of groups
- Multi-stakeholder partnerships
- Bringing in new partners for the university
- Obtaining internal resources

How did you succeed in your institution? What are good strategies?

- Bottom-up initiatives
- Starting at a low level and taking step by step (first bringing people together, then training as next step, ...)
- Support of the top management is key
- Funding is a change maker
- Funding programmes are an incentive
- Onboarding library staff
- Internal capacity building
- Constant support
- Support in grant writing
- Advocacy for citizen science within the university
- Recognition of team science (see Academia in Motion at Leiden University, <https://www.universiteitleiden.nl/en/news/2021/01/academia-in-motion-a-different-form-of-recognition-and-reward>)

What are the barriers to introduce citizen science in a research performing organisation?

- Research evaluation and reward systems change very slowly
- Hybrid roles (data steward, communication specialist,) are not recognised in the career so far, roles in a university are still strictly separated
- Recognition takes place at the national level
- Less high-impact journal publications (as a consequence of time constraints)
- A broad range of skills is needed, especially in terms of communication (e.g. publishing in non-academic journals or media)

What kinds of structure can be appropriate to organise citizen science support in institutions? What should institutions do to support citizen science?

- Not one recipe for all, because universities are very contextual
- Structure is not essential

- Communication and hands-on training or material is needed
- Libraries should flag out skills more
- Building diverse teams

Citizen science requires different kinds of expertise. How to cope with this?

- Capacity building within the university is important, e.g. ethical boards are often not so familiar with citizen science, legal and ethical questions are being raised more and more frequently
- Fostering transdisciplinary research
- Networking and empowering public libraries

How do cultural differences influence the application of citizen science? Is it different to implement citizen science in Western Europe from Eastern or Southern Europe?

- Research culture has an influence; participatory research practices are common in Spain; citizen science is at an early stage in Lithuania

How important are infrastructures?

- Community access is key (no publications behind the paywall)
- Communication tools or platforms for (equity-based exchange between citizens and researchers) play an important role

In which way should institutions be supported by local, regional and national governments and the EU?

- Supporting national citizen science conferences
- Serving as data aggregators (e.g. citizen science for environmental protection)
- Establishment and long-term provision of shared platforms on a national level
- Policy-uptake in decision-making
- Integrating citizen science in public administration (not only with regard to biodiversity, but also social issues)

Key findings of the panellists include:

- Important success factors include bottom-up initiatives, pilot projects, adequate and sustainable funding, as well as support from management, the involvement of library staff, and the importance of recognising achievements beyond traditional research assessment.
- There is a need for capacity building within the universities and for the recognition of the broad range of skills needed in citizen science projects. In that context, libraries should emphasise their expertise more strongly.
- The collaboration between public and university libraries should be encouraged.

Simone Rehm, the Co-Chair of the Task Force Openness of Science & Technology and Vice-Rector at the University of Stuttgart, concluded the session by first underlining that the Citizen Science Subgroup, initiated two years ago, became an integral part of the Task Force Openness of Science & Technology. She then summarised three key points from the discussion:

It is crucial for citizen science initiatives to benefit from the support of the leadership of the university.

Citizen science is extremely contextual, we can learn from best practices, but there are no standard procedures and approaches.

It is such good fun!

The Workshop was organized by Beate Guba (TU Wien) with Justine Moynat (CESAER) and Members of the CESAER Task Force Openness of Science & Technology –. Date of release of DOC: 11th October 2023.

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